

THE EFFECT OF CYCLIC WATER TEMPERATURE ON FLEXURAL PROPERTY OF UNSATURATED POLYESTER RESIN UNDER LIQUID AND VAPOR PHASE

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1 Introduction

Polymer composites have highly gained attention because of their high strength to weight ratio reduces gross weight [1]. The well-known applications that required light weight with high mechanical properties, such as Boeing 787 Dreamliner or body of automobile. On the other hand, FRP is also widespread used in chemical plant as its high chemical resistant and easy to construction. Comparing to metallic material, FRP possess a higher chemical durability and lighter weight which used as a chemical storage tank or chemical vessel for transportation which can contain severe chemical solution, such as hydrochloric acid or sulfuric acid. However, the limitation of FRP is that it should be used under low/normal operation condition (temperature, pressure). As a consequence, there is a great need to understand the mechanisms by which these materials respond to involve either solar ultraviolet (UV), freezing (snowing), other chemicals as reactants or catalysts, pressure, gases, or more than one of these combination. Polymeric material may subject to complex environmental conditions during their operational life, including exposure to water, chemicals, and temperature fluctuations, that affect their long service life time [2, 3].

In recent years, FRP has been used extensively in the production of piping and vessel for a wide range of chemical processing plant. Typically, FRP chemical tanks lifetime is expected to be 10-25 years in service, however, some accidents which a top roof of tank failure at less than expected life have been recently reported, which is shown in Fig.1.

Generally, many researchers reported that materials under liquid phase may show more severe condition than vapor phase in chemical storage tank. Time of exposure, concentration of solution, temperature of solution are varied and studied. Bovey F.A. and Winslow F.H. [15] mentioned that when relative humidity exceeds above 70%, the rate of polymer degradation by the microorganism increase. High temperature and high humidity enhance hydrolytic degradation of the polymers. M.K. Mahmoud and S.H. Tantawi [16] also reported that when polyester exposed to 1M sulfuric acid, the ultimate flexural strength retention reduces to approximately 90% after 4 days of exposure to 20% H₂SO₄.

Fig.1. The failure of chemical roof top containing hydrochloric acid.

However, those accidents were contrary to expectation from general knowledge. Therefore, comprehensive study on the material durability over a wide range of temperature and more severe condition is required [4].

Temperature change during a day or season is considered and it may make dynamic condition of vapor phase which expected a possibility of severe degradation. Basically, gaseous will start to evaporate at higher temperature, then condense into a liquid at lower temperature. At dew point temperature or saturated condition, gaseous will start to condense at a surface of material that may cause serious corrosion problems for the equipment. Moreover, vapor phase is more sensitive to temperature change during a day, comparing to liquid phase. Hence, temperature fluctuation may lower mechanism properties of material and lead to a failure of roof top's accident.

Hence, to investigate the effect of static and dynamic on polymer degradation this study aimed to study degradation behavior of polymeric material under both isothermal and cyclic solution temperature on both liquid phase and vapor phase. This study was periodically investigate not only mass uptake but also flexural strength to comprehend the long-term properties of composites.

2 Theoretical backgrounds

Many researchers had reported about the diffusion of moisture into polymeric materials. The classical simple limiting case of diffusion is expressed by Fick's equation [4-11].

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right) \quad (1)$$

where C represents the moisture concentration in unit polymer column at specific location from the surface x and time t . D is the moisture diffusion coefficient in the x direction. If the diffusion coefficient D is constant, the diffusion process will follow the Fickian type diffusion. In some case, D depends on concentration or other factors.

In general, at the initial stage of sorption process, the weight change in polymer-permeate systems has been demonstrated to follow a power law expression of time of the form:

$$\frac{W_t}{W_\infty} = Kt^m \quad (2)$$

where W_t and W_∞ are the experimental weight change or mass uptakes at the time t and equilibrium time ∞ , respectively, K is a constant dependent upon the structural characteristics of the polymer and its interaction with the solvent, and an exponent m is related to the transport mechanism as follows:

$$m = 0.5; \text{ Fickian transport}$$

$$m = 1.0; \text{ Case II transport}$$

$$0.5 < m < 1.0; \text{ anomalous transport}$$

In case of Fickian diffusion for flat plate subjected both sides permeation, K is approximately defined as:

$$K = \frac{4 \left(\frac{D}{\pi} \right)^{0.5}}{L} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{W_t}{W_\infty} = \frac{4(Dt)^{0.5}}{L\sqrt{\pi}} \quad (4)$$

where L is the thickness of specimen. For example, this simplified solution can be applied for the initial stage of sorption process, that is the plot of W_t/W_∞ vs $t^{0.5}$ should be linear up to $W_t = 0.6W_\infty$ with less than 2% deviation for true Fickian diffusion. Therefore, the diffusion coefficient, D , can be calculated from initial linear slope of the curves [5-8, 11-14].

3 Experiments

3.1 Material

- Iso-phthalic acid type unsaturated polyester resin with 6% of cobalt naphthenate (Rigolac 2141B, Showa Denko K.K.)

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The ratio of resin and MEKPO was 100:1. A mixing procedure was 600 phr for 2 minutes following by de-gas process for 10 minutes. A curing method was 50°C for 6 hours and 100°C for 6 hours. After finishing curing procedure to make 2mm thick plate, specimen was prepared as 25x60x2 mm, and then dried at 50°C for 10 days to ensure that the remaining moisture was removed and weight was not changed before carried out an experimental. Shape and dimension of specimen are shown in Fig.2.

Fig. 2. A dimension of prepared specimen.

3.2 Diffusion study

3.2.1 Moisture absorption

To measure the change of weight, each specimen was removed from the environment conditioning chamber, then whipped out by paper before measuring weight change. The moisture uptake or percent weight gain was calculated by equation (5).

$$\text{Mass uptake (\%)} = (M_t - M_0) / M_0 \times 100 \quad (5)$$

where M_t = Mass uptake of water at time t

M_0 = Dry weight of the initial sample

3.3 Conditioning solution temperature

3.3.1 Thermal cyclic condition

To study about the effect of cyclic solution temperature on polymeric material, new chamber for immersion test has been developed to control temperature of solution which shown in Fig. 3 and 4. A solution temperature is heated up by mantle heater and cooled by cooling coil which surround the vessel. This cooling coil and condenser was connected to cooling water circulator system that

kept at 20°C. In Fig. 5, it shows a heating/cooling rate of one cyclic segment which is set to fluctuate from 40°C to 80°C in 4 hours. Each conditioning temperature was kept for 1 hour, and both increasing and decreasing period were set to be 1 hour. According to a day and night time, this study carried out by three cyclic segments, 4 hours per segment as mentioned above, and following by keeping 20C for 12hours which totally equals to 24 hours, as shown in Fig. 6. However, it is still difficult to control a solution temperature to follow with just desired temperature. Furthermore, inside of this chamber contained specimens under both liquid phase (immersion) and vapor phase (evaporation) in order to investigate the mass uptake and mechanical properties in each sphase.

Fig. 3. The overall design of new testing chamber.

Fig. 4. The new designed chamber to control temperature of solution.

Fig. 5. Schematic diagram of a thermal cycle containing two isothermal holds and two dynamic heating/cooling segments.

Fig. 6. Schematic diagram of a thermal cyclic condition for twenty four hours.

3.3.2 Isothermal condition

For the isothermal condition, a solution temperature was constantly kept in a water bath. A glass container contained solution and specimens. Specimens were supported by fluororesin tube in both liquid and vapor phase, as shown in Fig. 7.

3.4 Mechanical Property

Flexural properties; elastic modulus and strength were used to examine mechanical properties of

ageing sample at different time according to ASTM D790 (by Shimadzu Autograph AGS-1KNJ machine, crosshead speed at 2 mm/min). Flexural test was performed at room temperature after specimens placed in room about 4 hours when temperature return close to atmosphere.

Fig. 7. The water bath used to study the effect of isothermal condition.

3.5 Fracture surface morphology

The technique of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is the most widely used method of studying fracture surface morphology. SEM observation on cross-section of specimen after performing bending test was conducted. A magnification was varied from 20-200 μ m.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Water absorption

To observe the effect of water absorption under isothermal and cyclic solution condition, weight change of specimen was examined. Isothermal condition was kept at 60°C and 80°C. Cyclic solution temperature was fluctuated between from 40°C to 80°C.

4.1.1 Mass uptake by water solution

Fig. 8 showed the percentage of mass uptake by isothermal at 60°C and 80°C condition. The results showed that the rate of mass uptake by isothermal condition on both liquid and vapor phases at early stage are nearly the same. Moreover, the percentage of mass uptake at saturation of both liquid phase and vapor phase by isothermal at 80°C was also similar. However, the percentage of mass uptake of specimen by isothermal at 80°C was higher than specimen by isothermal at 60°C. Since water at

higher temperature possess higher energy to penetrate into free volume of polymer.

Fig. 8. The percentage of mass uptake by water solution under liquid phase and vapor phase by isothermal condition at 60°C and 80°C.

Fig. 9 showed the results of mass uptake under cyclic solution temperature in liquid and vapor phase. Water temperature under cyclic solution temperature was fluctuated between 40°C to 80°C for 12 hours and keeping stable at 20°C for 12 hours as 1 cycle. The rate of mass uptake was gradually increased with increasing time, and then the rate of mass uptake was slightly lower after 48 hours. The percentage of mass uptake of specimen under liquid phase by cyclic solution temperature was almost stable after 100 hours, but specimen under vapor phase still increased. However, the rate of mass uptake by isothermal condition was higher than by cyclic solution temperature.

4.2 Mechanical properties

4.2.1 Isothermal & cyclic solution condition

Fig. 10 shows that flexural strength of specimens under liquid phase by both isothermal and cyclic solution temperature condition. Two lines indicate same tendency that both flexural strengths under isothermal and cyclic solution temperature were

immediately decreased and to be stable after 48 hours. The decreasing in flexural strength would be explained that after materials absorbed some water, then interchain of hydrogen bonding was reduced or scissor by absorbed water. Adamson [17] explained that when water is absorbed by a polymeric material, the comparatively small water molecules must either occupy the free volume of the epoxy or swell the polymer. Hahn [18] reported that the absorbed water produces relatively little swelling, which can weaken a material performance, until reaching saturation stage.

Fig. 9. The percentage of mass uptake by water solution under liquid phase and vapor phase by thermal cyclic solution condition and cyclic solution temperature segment.

On the other hand, the result of specimens under vapor phase by both isothermal condition and cyclic solution temperature is shown in Fig. 11. The tendency of flexural strength of specimen under vapor phase by isothermal condition at 80°C was similar to the result of specimen by liquid phase as the flexural strength is decreased and showed stable after mass uptake reaches near a saturation stage. However, the result of flexural strength of specimen under vapor phase by cyclic solution temperature showed slow decreasing with time. Since the percentage of mass uptake under vapor phase by

cyclic solution temperature has still not reached the saturation stage, so water or moisture can further diffuse into polymer structure.

Fig. 10. Flexural strength under liquid phase by water solution.

Fig. 11. Flexural strength under vapor phase by water solution.

The continue absorption might be assumed that would lower a performance of material. This absorbed water or moisture can extend to interact with hydrophilic site of polymer network that affected the interchain bonding of polymer.

On the other hand, the results of flexural modulus under liquid and vapor phase by both isothermal and cyclic solution temperature were only slightly decreased after long testing time, as shown in Figs.

12 and 13. Since it is well known that unsaturated polyester has a highly crosslinked network. Hence, chain scission such as hydrolysis was not occurred at temperature.

Fig. 12. Flexural modulus under liquid phase by water solution.

Fig. 13. Flexural modulus under vapor phase by water solution.

4.3 Morphology study

Figs. 14 and 15 showed the cross-section morphology of specimen under vapor phase by cyclic solution temperature at 24, 48 and 192 hours.

For fracture surface in Fig. 14 at early stage (straight slope line of the percentage of mass uptake as shown in Fig.8), uniformly flat surface can be

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observed at the tension side, but difference layer at compression side. However, after the rate of mass uptake was lower, as shown in Fig. 15, the fracture surface on tension side showed a white layer near

the surface of cross-section. When this white layer was enlarged, microcavities and microvoids can be detected.

Fig. 14. The cross section morphology under vapor phase by cyclic solution temperature at 24 hours.

Fig. 15. The specimen's cross section fracture morphology under vapor phase by cyclic solution temperature at 48 and 192 hours.

5. Conclusions and Discussions

An extensive study on the effect of cyclic solution temperature on polymeric material was conducted. The specimens were examined under fluctuated solution temperature condition and compared with isothermal immersion tests. Basically, vapor phase is more sensitive when atmospheric temperature change than liquid phase. Since vapor phase has lower heat capacity, so vapor phase is more sensitive to the outside temperature change. The sudden change in temperature was assumed to decrease a performance of material as the failure of rooftop of chemical tank was reported. Although many researchers reported that a material under liquid phase might decrease the properties more than vapor phase. Moreover, a rate of polymeric material degradation may faster if solution temperature is increased. However, a little researcher reported about the cyclic solution temperature condition on polymeric material.

According to the results of mass uptake in Figs. 8 and 9, the mass uptake of specimens under vapor phase by cyclic solution temperature was not reached the saturation stage even near 200 hours, compared with other results that can observe a saturation stage. This could be that evaporated water in vapor phase during heating/cooling can condense into a liquid on the surface of specimen, so further moisture or water can penetrate into polymer. The flexural strength of specimens under vapor phase by cyclic solution temperature was slightly decreased and lower than the flexural strength of specimen under liquid phase and both liquid and vapor phase by isothermal condition at 80°C, as shown in Fig. 10 and 11. This found out can point out the failure of rooftop of chemical storage tank that can be affected by the effect of cyclic solution temperature. As it showed weaken in a performance of material in vapor phase, compared with liquid phase. Nevertheless, the fracture morphology of specimen's cross-section can detected microcavities and microvoids that crack can easily propagate near the inner surface of specimen's cross-section, as shown in Fig. 14 and 15.

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